

Semi-Structured Interview Questions

1. What is the average age of the clients you speak to who have dealt with childhood trauma?
2. Do you speak to more male or female clients who have experienced childhood trauma?
3. What type of trauma has been mostly experienced by your clients?
4. What relationship did clients have with those who exposed them to traumatizing situations?
5. Have clients mentioned the age when they realised that the situation, they were exposed to during their childhood was not good for them?
6. Have clients talked about how they felt during their difficult times?
7. Have you noticed any patterns in the behaviour or attitudes of your clients following their traumatizing experiences?
8. Have clients expressed their own personal views of themselves?
9. What are some of the ways that childhood trauma victims commonly cope with their past?
10. Has any reference been made to the client's social background either by yourself or by the individual?